

Functional Footprint and its Role in Reducing the Manifestations of Chaos in the Organizational Work Environment

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ABSTRACT: This study sought to know the role of the functional fingerprint in reducing and supporting the manifestations of chaos in the work environment. The study relied on the descriptive analytical approach. The main research problem revolved around a basic question: Does the functional fingerprint have a role in reducing the manifestations of chaos in the work environment? The study focused on two main hypotheses that assume that there is a correlation and impact between the functional fingerprint and the manifestations of chaos in the work environment. Sadr Medical City was chosen as a community to apply the study and the medical staff working in it. The sample of the study consisted of (185) respondents. The questionnaire was used as a main tool for data collection and was analyzed by the (spssv.23) program. The study reached a set of conclusions, the most important of which are: There is a positive correlation between the functional fingerprint and the manifestations of chaos in the work environment, and this indicates The job imprint left by the employee in his field of work has an effective and important role in reducing the manifestations of chaos in the work environment , as well as the existence of a positive impact relationship between the job imprint and the manifestations of chaos in the work environment. This means that reducing the effectiveness of the manifestations of chaos in the work environment requires the presence of competent and effective administrative leaders in the field of harmonizing between the internal and external environment and identifying the most important problems and challenges and diagnosing the strengths and weaknesses of the organization. The current study confirmed that the medical staff in the research organization has high indicators of the job imprint in a way that contributes to reducing the manifestations of chaos in the work environment at the level of environmental complexity, environmental mobility and environmental uncertainty.

KEYWORDS: Job fingerprint, manifestations of chaos in the work environment, Sadr Medical City.

INTRODUCTION

Rapid and continuous changes are the dominant characteristic of the work environment in today's business world, which requires these organizations to adopt new and advanced approaches and methods that work to detect these changes and the ability to keep pace and adapt to them. This falls on the shoulders of executive leaders or senior management in organizations, through the efforts of employees to harmonize or adapt between the requirements of the internal environment and the external environment in a sustainable manner to keep pace and follow up on changes in the business environment and adapt to it strategically. The importance of the functional fingerprint is constantly increasing because it is a method that works to support the organization in several areas, the most important of which is continuous improvement, growth, development, quality and survival as a high strategic capacity. Thus, it enhances the support of the internal environment and contributes to reducing the levels of manifestations of chaos in the work environment. The study sought to explore the nature of the relationship between the functional fingerprint and the manifestations of chaos in the work environment. The variable of the functional fingerprint represents the unique and distinctive impact of the individual in his field of work, and consists of a special mix of skills, experiences, values, and work style adopted by the individual, which distinguishes him from others in the work environment. The functional fingerprint depends on The special talents and abilities that the individual possesses that contribute to his professional success, in addition to the lessons and experiences he acquires during his career that enhance his understanding and guidance in his field of work, as well as have an important role in promoting the principles and ethics that the individual espouses that affect his way of dealing with the requirements of work and colleagues, as well as the unique way in which he accomplishes his tasks such as ways of communication, cooperation, and problem solving. This imprint not only helps distinguish the individual from his colleagues, but also contributes to achieving self-confidence and improving the chances of success and professional progress. It can also positively affect the reputation and position of the individual. In the contemporary world, where competition in the labor market is increasing, the functional footprint becomes an important tool for excellence and impact that enables individuals with clear and distinct skills and capabilities to be more able to influence their fields and achieve success. To achieve this goal, the study was

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divided into four main sections. The first section included the scientific methodology of the research and the second section was devoted to the theoretical framework of the research variables. The third section dealt with the field framework of the research and finally included the fourth section of the most important conclusions and recommendations reached by the study.

The first topic

Procedural structure of research

This topic deals with identifying the problem of research, its importance and purpose, the hypothesis outline and hypotheses, which are:

First: the research problem

Human resources management is one of the most important resources on which organizations are based in the contemporary business environment. There is no doubt that the functional footprint is one of the most important means that executive managers must leave in an interactive work environment whose primary focus is on organizational performance and working efficiently and effectively to reduce the manifestations of chaos in the work environment. Leaders work to provide, develop and innovate knowledge in the internal work environment with what is in the external environment and keep pace with and adapt to it. This is because the dominant characteristic of the external environment is accelerated change. This requires the leaders of organizations to leave a footprint that contributes to addressing the problems facing workers in performing their work tasks, providing a safe and appropriate work environment based on trust and cooperation. Thus, the research problem crystallized in identifying the nature of the relationship between these variables through the main question of the study, which states: Does the functional footprint have role in reducing the manifestations of chaos in the work environment in the researched organization?

The following sub-questions are derived from this question:

1. What is the level of availability of the functional fingerprint in the researched organization?
2. What is the level of availability of the dimensions of the manifestations of chaos in the work environment in the organization in question?
3. Is there a significant correlation between the functional footprint and the manifestations of chaos in the work environment?
4. Is there a significant impact relationship between the functional footprint and the manifestations of chaos in the work environment?

Second: The importance of research

The importance of the current research lies in the fact that it touched on a vital and important topic and that many business organizations and public service organizations are in dire need of it, especially in the Iraqi environment. The importance of the research is summarized in the following points:

1. The importance of the research is embodied in providing a theoretical and practical framework for the variables of the functional fingerprint and the manifestations of chaos in the work environment that helps medical staff to understand its contents.
2. The importance of the research is highlighted in providing the research organization (Sadr Medical City) with clear information on the level of availability of the concept and dimensions of the functional fingerprint of medical staff in the university work environment.
3. The importance of the research is reflected in the definition of the research organization of the true level of availability of the dimensions of the manifestations of chaos in the work environment, and the extent to which this level needs to be reduced by the senior leaders in the hospital as a fundamental pillar of organizational stability.
4. The importance of the research is shown by the vital importance of its main and sub variables (the functional fingerprint and the manifestations of chaos in the work environment) as important and contemporary entrances to achieve organizational stability and sustainable strategic success.

Research objectives:

Guided by the content of the research problem and its questions, the current research aims to identify the role of the functional fingerprint in reducing the manifestations of chaos in the organizational work environment. The objectives of the research are as follows:

1. Determine the level of availability of the functional fingerprint in the researched organization.
2. Diagnose the level of indicators of the manifestations of chaos in the work environment in the research organization.
3. Ensure that there is a correlation between the functional fingerprint and the indicators of the manifestations of chaos in the work environment.
4. Ensure that there is an impact relationship between the functional fingerprint and the indicators of the manifestations of chaos in the work environment.
5. Work to submit a number of proposals based on the results of the research that would develop the variable of the functional fingerprint to reduce the manifestations of chaos in the work environment in future studies carried out by researchers wishing to delve into the variables of the current research in depth.

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Fourth: Research chart

In light of the research problem, and to achieve its objectives, the hypothetical scheme of the research was designed in a way that reflects the nature of the relations between the research variables, as the functional fingerprint variable is an independent variable and its dimensions were determined based on the model of (Monica Higgins) citing (Manhal, 2021), while the variable of the manifestations of chaos in the work environment is an approved variable and its dimensions were determined based on the model of (Al-Hakim and Al-Obaidi, 2022). The hypothetical scheme of the research is as follows:

Figure (1) The descriptive research schema

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on the measurement tool

Fifth: Research hypotheses:

Hypotheses represent expected claims that are consistent in their directions with what has been diagnosed in the research problem and the questions raised for the research problem. The hypotheses of the current research have been formulated in a new way that is consistent with the directions of the research and its practical analysis by testing the relationship and indirect impact of the functional fingerprint and the manifestations of chaos in the work environment and through **statistical inference of hypotheses and** to complete the requirements of the research. In order to answer its questions, a set of hypotheses have been developed that crystallize into two basic hypotheses of the current research:

1. The first main hypothesis: There is a statistically significant correlation between the functional fingerprint and the manifestations of chaos in the work environment at the macro level and the sub-dimensions in the studied organization.

The following sub-hypotheses follow:

- There is a statistically significant correlation between capabilities and reducing the manifestations of chaos in the work environment.
- There is a statistically significant correlation between links and reducing the manifestations of chaos in the work environment.
- There is a statistically significant correlation between perception and reducing the manifestations of chaos in the work environment.
- There is a statistically significant correlation between trust and reducing the manifestations of chaos in the work environment.

2. The second main hypothesis: There is a statistically significant impact relationship between the functional footprint and reducing the manifestations of chaos in the work environment at the macro level and the sub-dimensions in the surveyed organization.

The following sub-hypotheses follow:

- there is a statistically significant impact relationship between capabilities and reducing the manifestations of chaos in the work environment.

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B-There is a statistically significant impact relationship between links and reducing the manifestations of chaos in the work environment.

C. There is a statistically significant relationship between perception and reducing the manifestations of chaos in the work environment.

D. There is a statistically significant relationship between trust and reducing the manifestations of chaos in the work environment.

Sixth: Methods of data collection

The current research relied on the following methods of data collection

1. Methods of the theoretical side: In this aspect, the researcher relied on the analytical methods of the most important available from foreign sources, specifically on scientific research published in solid scientific journals, especially research directly related to the main and subsidiary research variables, as well as benefiting from the International Information Network and the Internet.

2. Practical (field) methods: The questionnaire was used as the main means of collecting data and information from the research community and sample. The questionnaire was designed according to the research objectives and hypotheses, including two main parts. The first part of the questionnaire focused on general information related to the personal data of the respondent. The second part included the main research variables and their sub-dimensions. The five-point Likert scale was used to determine the answer to the questionnaire paragraphs, which consists of five cases: (I do not completely agree, I do not agree, I am neutral, I agree, I agree completely).

Research Methodology:

The current research relied on the descriptive-analytical approach in order to adapt this approach to the nature and objectives of the research and thus help the researcher to be close to reality and can describe the phenomena accurately and clearly.

Eighth: Research Society and Sample

The study community was represented by the employees in Sadr Medical City in Najaf Governorate, as the medical staff represented by the head of the hospital, his assistants, and the heads of the people and units in Sadr Medical City and its affiliated formations. Thus, the total number of employees in Sadr Medical City is (350) and this represents the research community. As for the research sample, it was (185) employees in Sadr Medical City and at various addresses and medical, administrative and technical levels.

Ninth: Testing the stability of the measuring instrument

The researcher designed the questionnaire initially after reviewing a set of studies in the field of functional fingerprinting and manifestations of chaos in the work environment. The apparent validity and authenticity of the content was confirmed through the use of a method of control for a group of specialists and academics. As for the stability of the measurement tool (questionnaire form), the Cronbach Alpha coefficient was used as in the following table (1):

Table (1) Testing the stability of the measuring instrument

NO	Main Parameter	Number of Items:	Alpha Cronbach Values
1	Functional Footprint	16	.885
2	Manifestations of chaos in the work environment	12	0.873
3	Full Scale	28	0.886

Source: Preparation of the researcher based on the outputs of (Spss. ver. 23)

It is clear from the results of Table (1) that the research scale is characterized by high stability, and that all paragraphs of the scale are characterized by internal consistency, and this indicator qualifies the research tool for subsequent statistical tests.

Tenth: Research Limits

The boundaries of research can be divided into the following:

1. Spatial boundaries: The current research was applied in the field in Sadr Medical City in Najaf Governorate.

2. Time limits: The current research period was limited to its theoretical and field aspects for the period from 1\10\2023 to 1\8\2024.

3. Scientific limits: The scientific limits of the research on its main variables (functional fingerprint, aspects of chaos in the work environment).

4. Human Boundaries: A number of employees in Sadr Medical City have been identified as human boundaries for research, focusing on (the hospital director and his assistant, the heads of departments, divisions and units in the hospital, a number of doctors, administrators and technicians).

Eleventh: Statistical Processing Methods

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In order to reach the required results from the research, Spss.v.23 was selected as one of the important statistical programs in statistical analysis.

Section Two

Theoretical framework for research variables

Functional footprint and chaos in the organizational work environment

First: Functional fingerprint

1. Functional Footprint Concept

The concept of the functional footprint is an important topic in many areas, including the organizational environment and has been applied to several levels of analysis, from the organization to the individual (Christopher & András, 2013)

The functional footprint is the process through which individuals in organizations cultivate and acquire common sets of skills and characteristics that are specific to time and place. The concept of footprint is recognized through what we call its four constituent elements:

1. Capabilities, which are the skill sets we acquire.
2. Communications, or networks and alliances.
3. Confidence in certain ways of learning.
4. Being aware of what we are learning or assuming about the best ways to work towards our goals.

The functional footprint of an organization can be determined by looking at the types of work experiences people have in a given organization; therefore, different organizations, even those belonging to the same industry or sector, can cultivate different types of organizational functional footprints (Higgins, 2009:45). Functional footprint is defined as the abilities, connections, confidence, and perception that groups of people develop as a result of a common set of job experiences in a particular organization. Functional footprint is a phenomenon at the organizational level represented by the impact of culture, socialization processes, extended opportunities, and apparent success on people during the first stage of their careers (Hugh & Gunz, 2007:79). The job imprint serves as a lens for managerial experience as the individual imprint highlights that some work experiences can have a lasting impact on individuals and typifies tangible elements such as skills, knowledge, and social capital that people carry with them from one job to another (Marquis and Tilcsik 2013:156). The skills and knowledge acquired across careers form an integral part of a person's job identity. These experiences not only affect technical skills and information, but also extend to more subjective aspects such as expectations, preferences, and standards adopted by individuals. These subjective elements may not be directly obvious, but they have a significant and lasting impact on career, so belonging to a particular profession can deepen and shape the way people think and behave, as the profession imposes its standards, values, and traditions on its members. (Bourmault & Anteby, 2020:2) believes that preliminary research indicates that the values and expectations gained through a particular profession do not easily disappear even when people change jobs or take on new roles. For example, perceptions of managerial responsibility may stem not only from the characteristics of the current role, but also from the expectations and previous experiences that people carry with them. In light of the deep understanding of the concept of job fingerprint, we conclude that the feelings of responsibility experienced by new employees are affected not only by the requirements of the current job, but also by the expectations and previous experiences that have been transferred and formed during their previous job experiences. Functional footprint is defined as the process by which individuals acquire specific skills and characteristics within an organization, influenced by abilities, connections, trust, and perception. Different organizations can have different professional footprints (Sylvester & Donald, 2023:1).

Through the above, the researchers see that the job imprint is an expression used to describe the special and distinctive impact that an individual has in his profession. It consists of the skills, experiences, values, and work style that a person develops over the course of his career. It includes the way a person deals with his colleagues, how he performs tasks, the decisions he makes, and his impact on the culture of the organization or the environment in which he works. Thus, it represents a set of attributes that make the individual's performance unique and affect others and the organization as a whole. This imprint constitutes the functional identity of the individual and can be pivotal in his professional progress and influence in his field of work.

2. Importance of Functional Footprint in Business Organizations

We are all defined by our experiences, but we are not necessarily aware of how these experiences shape our future choices, so awareness of the job signature is a way to make this tangible. At work, the "fingerprints" we capture along the way will affect our preferences in the workplace and work style, what we value as competencies, and how we interact with others. Some will gravitate towards informal and entrepreneurial organizations and others to more structured environments; some will indulge in a particular field while others will opt for functional expertise. Although some communication styles are cultural norms, the choices we make about how we express ourselves through language and tone are often influenced by the functional imprint, and when we understand our functional imprints, we are simply better informed about the career choices we make. Then, as we move forward, some will be drawn to opportunities that reinforce what they already have and know. On the other hand, it is entirely possible for

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an individual to look for environments in which they can afford new fingerprints (Higgins,2009:82). The importance of fingerprint theory is highlighted in the way that sensitive experiences experienced by individuals and organizations affect the development of their characteristics and how they continue to reflect these characteristics over time, despite shifts in the surrounding environment. Studies have shown that footprint holds great importance for individuals and organizations alike, influencing factors such as the potential for organizations to grow and the rate of change in employees. Researchers also emphasize the role of footprint in individuals' lives, noting how mentors and colleagues at early stages of a career can shape the work choices they make later (Adam R.,2015:12). Footprint theory provides an analysis of how the values and practices adopted by individuals in a specific period affect their future behaviors. Research in the field of social entrepreneurship indicates that the backgrounds and previous experiences of individuals, interpreted through theories such as human capital, personality traits, organizational foundations, and behavioral theories in entrepreneurship, play a pivotal role in shaping their behavior. Recently, it has been shown that the social class fingerprints associated with footprint can affect the behaviors of entrepreneurs related to environmental sustainability, and the experience and education of executives, in turn, affect the orientation of organizations towards sustainable practices such as environmental innovation (Zhang,2022:4).

The importance of the functional fingerprint in terms of human resources as addressed by the researchers (Kitt & Sanders, 2022:5) As the functional fingerprint in human resources management plays a vital role in shaping the internal processes and strategies of organizations, and these fingerprints help determine how individuals are selected and recruited, and affect the way they are developed and motivated within the work environment. Awareness of it can promote conformity between the values of employees and the culture of the organization, which facilitates integration and enhances performance at the individual level. (Kitt & Sanders ;2022:18) adds that the job imprint helps identify the behaviors and skills that individuals bring to the workplace, and is useful in guiding training and development to improve these skills or develop new skills. At the organizational level, understanding the job imprint of employees can help identify strategies to maintain talent and reduce labor turnover, which contributes to the stability of the workforce and improves productivity. Understanding the functional footprint is also important in organizational change processes and strategic planning, as it can facilitate adaptation to new changes and effectively address challenges. (Rodrigues &Oliveira, 2021:91) believes that the job imprint contributes to reducing the negative culture of the organization, and reflects the values and ethics that support the commitment and loyalty of employees. In the end, the job imprint is an integral part of human resources management, and its appreciation and work is essential for success and sustainable progress in any organization.

3. Functional Fingerprint Dimensions

The functional footprint consists of four main dimensions that combine to determine how individuals respond to the functional challenges and opportunities presented to them by their organizations according to the Monica Higgins model in her book and quoting what the researcher (Manhal,2021:456) addressed. These dimensions include **capabilities**, which express the skills and knowledge that the individual possesses, and **linkages** that reflect the strength and structure of social relations inside and outside the organization, and **perception**, which represents the way in which individuals interpret and deal with information and experiences, and **finally confidence**, which refers to self-efficacy and a sense of security in the ability to perform and accomplish work. These dimensions constitute the framework that allows organizations to understand how functional experiences can contribute to the development of individuals and thus improve organizational performance by exploring each dimension separately and considering how they affect collectively. Organizations can reshape their policies and practices to promote and support a stimulating and productive work environment. The following is a brief explanation of these four dimensions:

A. Capacities

The ability represents the physical and mental ability of the individual to do something. "In dualistic philosophy, the individual is described as a formation of the body and the mind, while the individual's body is the material basis for the mind being the non-material part. Below is a set of other definitions of the concept of abilities. It explores the concept of capability in more detail and comes up with five possible explanations for capabilities: (personal tendencies, needs, skills available to each individual, individual traits, opportunities available) (Manhal,2021:45). The concept of individual capabilities from a human resources perspective deals with the development and exploitation of the individual capabilities and skills of employees within organizations. In the field of human resources, individual capabilities are seen as a critical element for the success and development of the organization. Modern human resources management focuses on identifying, developing, and exploiting the individual capabilities of employees to achieve the goals of the organization. This includes training and development, accurate evaluation of performance, and providing opportunities for career and personal development. Training and development are important to enhance the capabilities of employees by improving their current skills and providing new skills necessary to adapt to changes in the work environment. In addition, periodic evaluation of employee performance helps to identify strengths and weaknesses and provide appropriate guidance to improve performance. Individual capabilities in the context of human resources include a variety of aspects such as technical skills, knowledge, personal competencies, and social skills. Emphasis is also placed

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on the leadership and motivational capabilities of individuals, especially in management and leadership roles. In the end, the concept of individual capabilities in human resources aims to balance the objectives of the organization and the personal growth of employees, which leads to a more productive and satisfying work environment. Employees are encouraged to achieve their full potential, which benefits both the organization and employees in the long term (McKeown, E., 2021:12).

B. Links:

Links refer to types of social capital, including relationships within and outside the organization related to work and work completion, including the strength and structure of these links. Work links are defined as "the living fabric that exists between two people at work when there is some interaction involving mutual awareness." Links guide researchers to experience separate interactions that occur on a single occasion, or in specific contexts within an ongoing relationship between two people (for example, a conversation somewhere, an interaction on an issue in the meeting hall, or an apology from a specific situation). We focus on three main categories of communication mechanisms - cognitive, emotional and behavioral - as they are essential social and psychological pathways in building high-quality links at work: (Manhal,2021:52)

1. Cognitive connections: Cognitive mechanisms highlight how conscious and unconscious thought processes prepare individuals to build good connections at work.
2. Emotional Connections: Emotional mechanisms refer to how emotions open up communication between individuals and share those emotions between individuals in ways that build work connections.
3. Behavioral connections: Finally, behavioral mechanisms demonstrate the role of different types of individual actions that explain the quality of communication formed by two people.

C. Perception:

The term *cognoscere* comes from the Latin word *cognoscere*, which means "to know." Cognition was simply defined as "the ability to do the kinds of things that perceivers like us can do, in addition to the basic functional mechanisms for doing them." Cognition (the external part) of memory is a comprehensive term for phenomena that exist everywhere in our mental lives, for example: (acquiring and using a new language, performing and learning skills, communication and social communication, daily routine, and any other form of work).

(Dror & Harnad,2023:49) also explains their view of perception as representing thinking, understanding and knowledge. It expresses a state of mind, and it should be noted that systems that do not contain mental states, such as cognitive technology, can sometimes contribute to human perception, but this does not make them aware. (Manhal, 2021:821) believes that cognition in the context of enabling conditions for behavior provides a deeper understanding of the power of human organizations. This approach highlights the uniqueness of human social activity. This approach explores how both the overall organizational environment and individual dynamics affect social behavior within the organization. The intermediate domain, which links major and individual contexts, plays a pivotal role in enabling individuals to perceive within broader social and economic systems.

(Secchi, D., & Cowley, S. J.,2021:42) The emerging and evolving dynamics in complex systems is how different elements interact to form new behaviors and patterns. These dynamics can be examined through agent-based simulation models and ethnographic methods that use techniques such as video analysis and linguistic research. They are also explored through the study of human interaction and how it affects collective behavior. The intermediate domain is an essential component of organizational cognition because it provides the link between major and minor factors, allowing for a more accurate explanation of how different contexts affect cognition and behavior within organizations. This integrated understanding helps clarify the underlying processes driving social activity and its evolution within complex organizational environments.

D. Trust:

Self-confidence, or what is called in organizational research "self-efficacy", reflects the concept of the internal ideas of the individual about whether he has the ability or skill necessary to perform a specific task and turn this skill into good results. Self-confidence depends on individuals' self-perceptions of these skills and abilities within a specific field. Researchers usually note that we are usually excited about our perceptions about the capabilities we have rather than focusing on the actual current capabilities and that those perceptions affect both our behaviors and our emotional states. (Manhal,2021:1)

The concept of trust refers to the degree of belief or certainty an individual holds about the likelihood of success of various mental processes or actions. It expresses a sense of certainty or security about a person's abilities, judgments, or thoughts. Confidence can be understood in its general sense as a synonym for probability, such as estimating the probability that something will happen. In this context, a distinction is made between confidence as a sense of certainty about one's own actions or judgments, and certainty as a broader concept encompassing belief in a variety of quantities or phenomena (Fleming, S. M., 2023:1).

Second: Manifestations of chaos in the organizational work environment

1. The concept of manifestations of chaos in the organizational work environment

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The manifestations of chaos in the work environment are important topics in administrative and organizational research, as chaos in language is randomness, disorder and confusion, and the concept of chaos emerged from the field of biology in contrast to the Newtonian model, which was related to the fields of physics and mathematics (Tetenbaum & Laurence 2011:33). Through his work in weather systems, Lorenz made significant contributions to "chaos theory." In his research, chaotic systems have been defined as follows: processes that seem to run according to chance, even though their behavior is in fact determined by specific laws" (Lorenz 1993). To explore the meaning of chaos, the word itself is not chaos or randomness, chaos is order, but it is the invisible system, chaos is not just the result of noise or interference, or even insufficient knowledge, chaos includes the inherent "uncertainty principle" that is not similar to the way we look at the world, but rather resembles the way the world actually works and the new science of chaos that the environment is full of randomness and uncertainty, the environment is characterized by surprise, rapid change, and confusion and often seems out of control, and the focus of chaos is a network of feedback loops that exist in each system, in some systems, feedback loops are linear; in others, non-linear (Tetenbaum & Laurence 2011:22). As a key factor of chaos, the nonlinear dynamic system is a system in which the relationships between time-dependent variables are nonlinear and chaos as a system, it includes an open and uncontrollable position against random shocks of external stimuli, a behavior sensitive to the initial state in which it occurs, unpredictable behavior, and a non-cyclical process. Chaos theory, whose basic idea is shocking, does not refer to chaos or randomness, but to a system that is difficult to see and is the result of asymmetric information. What chaos means is a kind of natural uncertainty. It is even said that chaos represents a compromise between free will and determinism. Chaos theory has been discussed as a suitable model for creating a strategy in a combination of instability and unbalanced order in a rapidly changing business environment. It is applied in many fields of the social sciences such as economics, sociology, political science and organizational studies. While the rational approach claims that decision-making can be achieved successfully with complete and accurate information, chaos theory suggests that such a situation is very difficult. It is not available. Therefore, this entry changes the terms of reference for decision-making from administratively, it refers to the main role of the manager in learning the unbalanced conditions required for the new strategic management. The most important reason for the unpredictability of behavior in the chaotic system is that all factors that play a role in behavior cannot be fully determined and all elements of the system contain chaotic features (Taşgit et al.,2023:76). (Smith & Humphries, 2004:97) argue that ergonomic chaos is the behavior of the system as a whole and a complex product of multiple interactions and interventions by individual actors that are unpredictable. See (McBride, 2005: 4) Chaos is a concept that indicates the absence of organization. It is a disorder in which confusion and uncertainty prevail. Chaos is called organized disorder.

(IFont&Régis, 2006: 20) states that the manifestations of chaos are a dynamic system with a complex, irregular, and apparently non-periodic deterministic behavior characterized by randomness and lining the state of the system. According to (Parke & stacy, 2007:11), chaos is a mixture of order, order, consistency, and asymmetry, a pattern of behavior that is inconsistent but recognizable as a broad pattern of behavior and archetypes within an endless individual diversity.(Velasquez, 2009:14) adds that organizational chaos is a random behavior of systems resulting from sensitivity to initial conditions that gives them the property of unpredictability. Houry, 2012:229) believes that chaos is an event characterized by randomness that cannot be predicted in the long term at least, and it is a state of environmental complexity and unpredictability that prevails in any organization resulting from the excessive impact of the surrounding variables that lead to comprehensive chaos.

The researcher believes that the manifestations of chaos in the organizational work environment indicate a situation in which there is a lot of confusion and a lack of organization within the organization, which leads to inefficiency and sub-optimal performance. This occurs when the organization works in an isolated and unorganized manner.

2. The importance of studying the manifestations of chaos in the work environment in organizations

Many writers and researchers have focused on studying the issue of the manifestations of chaos in the work environment because of its importance as one of the most important modern variables in human resource management and organizational behavior and is critical to maintaining a positive and healthy culture in the workplace (Jaggarwal & Ahlawat, 2023:44). Managers and employees are often referred to as the custodians of organizational culture and can contribute to the development of a strong and positive workplace culture by following the procedures outlined below:

- A. Limit organizational values: Organizational values are limited by their behaviors that employees aspire to, and therefore they must demonstrate through their actions that they are abiding by the rules and plans of the organization.
- B. Maintain a reward and recognition system: The HR team should have the responsibility to assess and respect the people who are important to them. They must ensure that these individuals receive the appropriate reward and recognition.
- C. Encouraging and empowering teams: All teams in the organization are ultimately linked to human resources. As a result, it is the duty of this team to encourage other teams to give their best. They will be able to discover their talents and make good use of them.
- D. Provide training and learning: Employers must provide a continuous training program for their employees in this era of continuous change. It will keep them informed, and they will be prepared for new difficulties.

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3. Dimensions of chaos in the organizational work environment

The manifestations of chaos in the work environment are important, although there are significant differences in the orientations of researchers to determine the basic dimensions of the chaotic system, and the study of (Al-Hakim and Al-Obaidi, 2022: 453) will be relied upon in determining the dimensions of chaos in the organizational work environment, which are three dimensions:

A. Environmental complexity: It consists of three characteristics:

1. A complex system consists of a set of independent elements together
2. A set of interactions within the system can lead to the emergence of a spontaneous system based on self-regulation
3. The behavior of a complex system is influenced by feedback. It is a system consisting of a set of interacting elements that lead to the emergence of a new state based on self-regulation and feedback.

This system was often described as open, that is, open to the external environment and affected by external factors. Environmental complexity is divided into three groups:

1. The complexity of trust, which is similar to uncertainty, and this complexity is dealing with something unique, such as solving new problems or dealing with uncertainty to a high degree
2. Realistic complexity is like structural complexity and this complexity requires dealing with a very large number of interrelated information and this challenge is to maintain a holistic view of the problem and not to be lost in quantities of realistic details
3. The complexity of interaction usually occurs as a result of conflicts and interaction between members of the organization and organizational positions and responsibilities.

B. Environmental mobility:

Dynamic kinetics is defined as a set of stimuli and responses that occur within organizations in different situations experienced by the organization that are aware of the behaviors of emergency operations. An individual who issues a certain behavior within the organization is met with many responses from the rest of the individuals. Thus, social and psychological interaction occurs similar to a chemical interaction. Kinetics are classified into tangible and intangible. Concrete kinetics are also referred to as adaptive factors or connected mechanisms. These factors include simple and rapid mechanisms that allow for rapid response and rearrangement of the components of the system, as well as small mechanisms with a short-term focus guided by flexible strategies that share information inappropriately so as to adapt quickly through the rearrangement of components and thus facilitate the emergence of the organization. Intangible dynamics are referred to as social factors and are the factors that characterize human systems and are responsible for empowerment

C. Environmental Uncertainty:

Sensitivity to elementary conditions is a well-known phenomenon of non-linear systems, and it is one of the prominent signs of chaos. The concept of chaos indicates the absence of organization, a disorder in which confusion and uncertainty prevail, a field that may be strange to describe working in organizations in which the state of the system prevails. Therefore, the term chaos may be expressed as organized disorder, and the simulation that allows us to conduct hypothetical experiments. The actual experiences in the field of organization management show the characteristic of uncertainty and the need to overcome it. The importance of research tools such as models is often impossible, either because they require a very long time or because they will cause harm. Although accurate prediction may be impossible, simulation makes it possible to examine learning methods with several possible alternatives.

Section Three

Practical aspect of the research

First: Normal Distribution of Research Variables

Table (2) shows the nature of the lower and upper limits of the answers of the studied sample, which are limited between ((1) I do not completely agree) and ((5) I completely agree). This indicates to us that there are no answers outside these limits (abnormal values). In addition, all the values of the Kurtosis and Skewness coefficients are within the limits of (± 1.96), which confirms to us the distribution of the entire variable of the functional fingerprint and the manifestations of chaos in the work environment and their dimensions are naturally distributed and ready for subsequent statistical analyses.

Table (2) The values of kurtosis and torsion of the main and sub-search variables

Variable	Dimension	Sample	Values. The gay?	Adna answer	Highest Answer	Flattening coefficient Skewness	Modulus of torsion Kurtosis
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		Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Functional Footprint	Capacities	185	0.000	2.00	5.00	- 437.	.230	847	460
		185	0.000	2.00	5.00	.388	.230	- 214?	460
		185	0.000	2.00	5.00	417?	.230	- 214?	460
		185	0.000	2.00	5.00	- 501?	.230	.294	460
		185	0.000	2.00	5.00	635**	.230	115	460
	Codes	185	0.000	2.00	5.00	{\1cH4080FF}-555;	.230	.764	460
		185	0.000	2.00	5.00	421.	.230	554**	460
		185	0.000	2.00	5.00	095	.230	012	460
		185	0.000	2.00	5.00	- 214?	.230	.388	460
		185	0.000	2.00	5.00	265	.230	-0.759	460
	PERCEPTION	185	0.000	2.00	5.00	.718	.230	.018	460
		185	0.000	2.00	5.00	818	.230	-125	460
		185	0.000	2.00	5.00	394	.230	.801	460
		185	0.000	2.00	5.00	314	.230	785.	460
		185	0.000	2.00	5.00	0 - 999	.230	774	460
	Confidence	185	0.000	2.00	5.00	- 214?	.230	-972	460
		185	0.000	2.00	5.00	450	.230	.725	460
		185	0.000	2.00	5.00	314	.230	.647	460
		185	0.000	2.00	5.00	.278	.230	922	460
		185	0.000	3.00	5.00	621	.230	.698	460
Manifestations of chaos in the work environment	Environmental Complexity	185	0.000	2.00	5.00	.918	.230	812	460
		185	0.000	2.00	5.00	.698	.230	.511	460
		185	0.000	2.00	5.00	- 315.	.230	147	460
		185	0.000	2.00	5.00	.316	.230	.864	460
	Environmental mobility	185	0.000	2.00	5.00	519	.230	- 632.	460
		185	0.000	2.00	5.00	-.422	.230	0-411	460
		185	0.000	2.00	5.00	923	.230	0.222	460
		185	0.000	2.00	5.00	0-412	.230	.575	460
	Environmental uncertainty	185	0.000	2.00	5.00	853	.230	.364	460
		185	0.000	2.00	5.00	- \$825.	.230	128	460
		185	0.000	2.00	5.00	.536	.230	396	460
		185	0.000	2.00	5.00	458	.230	339	460
		185	0.000	2.00	5.00	0-412	.230	722	460
		185	0.000	2.00	5.00	.463	.230	-0.435	460
		185	0.000	2.00	5.00	-634.	.230	.547	460

Source: Preparation of the researcher based on the outputs of (Spss. ver. 23).

From Table (2), we note that all the values of the Kurtosis and Skewness coefficient fall within (± 1.96), which means that all the main and sub-search variables are normally distributed.

Second: Exploratory Factor Analysis of Research Variables

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When reviewing Table (3), we note that all the values of the saturation of the research paragraphs, which relate to the functional fingerprint variable, amounting to (16) paragraphs and the manifestations of chaos in the work environment, amounting to (12) paragraphs, and depending on the matrix of the basic components (Principal Components), which must exceed the permissible limits, which are (0.5), as explained below:

Table (3) Exploratory Factor Analysis of the Main and Sub-Variables of Research

Variable	Dimension	Paragraphs	Initial:	Extraction?	Variable	Dimension	Paragraphs	Initial:	Extraction?
Functional Footprint	Capacities	x11	1,000	0.768	Manifestations of chaos in the work environment	Environmental Complexity	Y11	1,000	0.636
		x12	1,000	0.697			Y12	1,000	0.610
		X13	1,000	0.737			Y13	1,000	0.539
		X14	1,000	0.691			y14	1,000	0.714
	Codes	x21	1,000	0.664		Environmental mobility	SL/ Y21	1,000	.725
		x22	1,000	0.655			Y22	1,000	0.794
		x23	1,000	0.611			Y23	1,000	0.632
		x24	1,000	609			Y24	1,000	754
	PERCEPTION	x31	1,000	0.603		Environmental uncertainty	Y31	1,000	.653
		x32	1,000	.788			y32	1,000	0.683
		x33	1,000	740			UNTRANSLATED CONTENT_START y33	1,000	.665
							UNTRANSLATED CONTENT_END		
	x34	1,000	.718	Y34		1,000	.729		
	Confidence	x41	1,000	775					
		x42	1,000	700					
		x43	1,000	0.712					
x44		1,000	0.636						

Source: Preparation of the researcher based on the outputs of (Spss. ver. 23).

We note from the data of Table (3) that the saturation values of all paragraphs of the functional fingerprint and the variable of the manifestations of chaos in the work environment and all their dimensions are more than (0.50), which means that they are distinctive and there is no need to delete any paragraph because there is no saturation less than the required limit (0.50), which means that all the main and sub variables are distinct and are ready for all subsequent statistical analysis.

Third: Descriptive Statistics of Research Variables

This paragraph will examine the descriptive statistics of the main and sub-search variables through the use of the weighted arithmetic mean, standard deviation and causal significance as in Table (4):

Table (4) Descriptive statistics of the main and sub-search variables

Variable	Dimension	Item	Mean	Standard deviation	Variable	Dimension	Item	Mean	Standard deviation
					UNTRANSLATED_CONTENT_START Importance				
					الانسدادية RTNU				
					ANSLATED_CONTENT_END				

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Functional Footprint	Capacities	X11	0.428	0.655	0.868	Manifestations of chaos in the work environment	Environmental Complexity	Y11	520	0.711	0.856
		X12	4.367	.713	0.836 *			Y12	4.065	0.757	0.851
		X13	4.980	0.723	.806			Y13	(3, 144)	0.691	.802
		X14	128	0.719	0.825			y14	328	0.956	809
	Codes	X21	0.964	.675	830.		Environmental mobility	SL/Y21	152	0.865	0.833
		X22	4,199	0.735	0.828			Y22	4.232	0.058	0.832
		X23	482	1.006	692			Y23	3.856	863	0.779
		X24	.864	.788	0.755			Y24	395	0.621	0.862
	PERCEPTION	X31	4.209	0.753	.834		Environmental uncertainty	Y31	158	700	0.712
		X32	4.200	.855	0.846			y32	384	0.796	0.825
		X33	3.258.00	0.968	0.752			UNTR ANSLATED CONTENT START y33 UNTR ANSLATED CONTENT_END	.963	0.801**	.776
		X34	631	0.892	0.732			Y34	4.090	0.055	0.843 ***
	Confidence	X41	.652	0.990	0.722						
		X42	.998	0.923	.782						

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	x	3.7	0.9	0.737					
	4	10	79						
	3								
	x	4.3	0.8	.806					
	4	25	18						
	4								

Source: Preparation of the researcher based on the outputs of (Spss. ver. 23).

From the data of Table (4), we note that all the values of the weighted mean were more than the hypothetical mean, which is (3) , which means that there is clarity in the examined sample towards all the research variables.

Fourth: Testing the correlation hypotheses:

The first main hypothesis: This hypothesis stated that there is a correlation between the functional fingerprint and the manifestations of chaos in the work environment at the macro level. Through the data of Table (5), we note that there is a positive correlation between the functional fingerprint and the manifestations of chaos in the work environment at the macro level of (0.638* *) at a significant level (0.000), and since the level of morale achieved is less than the assumed level of morale (0.05), so the first main hypothesis is accepted at the research level.

Table (5) Correlation coefficients between the main and sub-search variables

Independent Variables		Capacities	Codes	Perception	Confidence	Functional Footprint
Dependent variable	Pearson Correlation	.622**	.514**	Untranslated Content Start.655**Untranslated_Content End	.675**	1.638
in an enterprise environment	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	185	185	185	185	185

Source: Preparation of the researcher based on the outputs of (Spss. ver. 23).

After completing the test of the first sub-hypothesis, we will test the sub-hypotheses as follows:

1. There is a correlation between the counting of capabilities and the manifestations of chaos in the work environment at the macro level, through the data of Table (5), we note that there is a positive correlation relationship of (0.622* *) at a significant level (0.000) and since the level of significance achieved is less than the assumed level of significance (0.05), so the first sub-hypothesis is accepted at the current research level.
2. There is a correlation between the number of links and the manifestations of chaos in the work environment at the macro level, through the data of Table (5), we note that there is a positive correlation relationship of (0.514* *) with a significant level of (0.000), and since the level of significance achieved is less than the assumed level of significance (0.05), so the second sub-hypothesis is accepted at the current research level.
3. There is a correlation between the dimension of perception and the manifestations of chaos in the work environment at the macro level, through the data of Table (5), we note that there is a positive correlation of (0.655* *) at a significant level (0.000), and since the level of significance achieved is less than the assumed level of morale (0.05), so the third sub-hypothesis is accepted at the current research level.
4. There is a correlation between the dimension of trust and the manifestations of chaos in the work environment at the macro level, through the data of Table (5), we note that there is a positive correlation of (0.675* *) at a significant level (0.000) and since the level of morale achieved is less than the assumed level of morale (0.05), so the fourth sub-hypothesis is accepted at the current research level.

Fifth: Testing hypotheses of impact

The second main hypothesis: This hypothesis stated that there is an impact relationship for the functional fingerprint in the manifestations of chaos in the work environment at the macro level. Through the data of Table (6), we note that there is a positive impact relationship between the functional fingerprint and the manifestations of chaos in the work environment at the macro level

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of (0.638* *) and (T= 4.520) with a significance of (0.000), and since the level of morale achieved is less than the assumed level of morale (0.05), so this hypothesis is accepted at the research level.

Table (6) Influence coefficients between the functional fingerprint and the manifestations of chaos in the work environment

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	F	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
(Constant)	1.439	.308		520	0.000	.365	.000b
Functional Footprint	.618	-0.063	.638	.078	0.000		

Source: Preparation of the researcher based on the outputs of (Spss. ver. 23).

In addition, we note that the value of (F=65.365) with a moral level of (0.000) indicates the morale of the research model, which means that the job fingerprint actually affects the manifestations of chaos in the work environment, which means that all the research steps are correct. After completing the test of the main hypothesis of influence, we will come to test the sub-hypotheses and as in Table (7):

Table (7) Influence coefficients between the dimensions of the functional fingerprint and the manifestations of chaos in the work environment

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		standardized Coefficients	t.	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
Functional Footprint	(Constant)	207	323		642	522
	Capacities	369	.054	387	601	.000
	Codes	.087	.123	(061)	712	458
	PERCEPTION	351	102	295	UNTRANSLATED CONTENTSTART3.117UNTRANSLATEDCONTENTEND	.001
	Confidence	301	0.105 ***	.282	.675	-0.005 ***

Source: Preparation of the researcher based on the outputs of (Spss. ver. 23).

1. There is an impact relationship for the counting of capabilities in the variable of the manifestations of chaos in the work environment at the macro level, through the data of Table (7), we note that there is an impact relationship of (B= 0.387) and that the value of (T = 6.601) at a significant level (0.000) and since the level of significance achieved is less than the assumed level of significance (0.05), so the first sub-hypothesis of impact at the level of this research is accepted.
2. There is an impact relationship for the counting of links in the variable of the manifestations of chaos in the work environment at the macro level, through the data of Table (7), we note that there is an impact relationship of (B = -.061) and that the value of (T = 0.712 -) at a significant level (0.458) and since the level of morale achieved is greater than the assumed level of morale (0.05), so the second sub-hypothesis is rejected at the level of this research.
3. There is an effect relationship of the counting of perception in the variable of the manifestations of chaos in the work environment at the macro level, and through the data of Table (7) we note that there is an effect relationship of (B=0.295) and that the value of (T=3.117) at a significant level (0.001) and since the level of morale achieved is less than the assumed level of morale (0.05), so the third sub-hypothesis is accepted at the level of this research.

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4. There is an impact relationship of the counting of confidence in the variable of the manifestations of chaos in the work environment at the macro level, and through the data of Table (7) we note that there is an impact relationship of ($B=0.282$) and that the value of ($T=2.675$) at a significant level (0.005) and since the level of morale achieved is less than the assumed level of morale (0.05), so the fourth sub-hypothesis is accepted at the level of this research.

The fourth topic

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

First: Conclusion

The research reached a number of conclusions, the most important of which were the following:

1. The variable of the functional fingerprint is one of the modern scientific concepts in human resources management and has an important and effective role in reducing the manifestations of chaos in the work environment in the work environment as it contributes to achieving stability and organization of the work environment.
2. It was found that the organizational work strategy according to the criteria of the functional footprint often requires the support of senior management, as a decision must be made in support of the work environment in a way that corresponds to the needs and requirements of the work with the strategy of the organization to avoid all aspects of chaos and complications that occur within the organization.
3. Leaving the job imprint of leaders in the performance of their job tasks represents a high and supportive ability for an organization to respond to the competitive environment and confront environmental mobility and then maintain the harmony of its internal and external environment with various circumstances, challenges and different times.
4. The effects of the footprint in the work environment in accordance with sustainable human resources standards is of great importance in developing and understanding the vision of managers in supporting the leadership role in establishing strategic positions and actions that everyone attests to its excellence, which forms a fingerprint that supports and enhances communication, cooperation and coordination that focuses on reducing indicators of environmental uncertainty, as the consensus between the organizational levels gives a positive image on the footprint of medical staff that leads to commitment and facing complex and accelerated environmental changes.
5. The manifestations of chaos in the work environment directly affect the organizational climate and lead to instability that affects ideas, training programs and levels of experience and thus even affects organizational policies in general.
6. The employees' enjoyment of effective skills and capabilities has a role in providing the requirements that support the stability of the work environment, and guiding workers towards performing their work with high professionalism and in accordance with strong relations and links between co-workers that are supportive of achieving the policies and objectives of the organization.
7. Many of the basic pillars that provide a safe and stable work environment away from all aspects of chaos are the employee's sense of security and justice and staying away from complexity in performing job tasks, as well as participating in decisions and cooperation and creating an atmosphere of mutual trust between the boss and the subordinate are basic criteria for the stability of the work environment.
8. From the practical side, it became clear that there is a positive correlation and impact between the functional footprint to reduce the manifestations of chaos in the work environment in the researched organization.

Second: Recommendations

In light of the conclusions reached by the current research, there are a number of recommendations, the most important of which are:

1. The need for the research sample organization to raise indicators that would leave an imprint and a positive attitude among employees, and to consolidate this in the internal work environment because of its importance in reducing the manifestations of chaos in the work environment, supporting working individuals and facing environmental complexity as one of the indicators that contribute to creating chaos in the organization and affect its stability.
2. The researched organization should strive seriously and genuinely to support the dimensions of the functional footprint effectively to take its role in reducing the manifestations of chaos in the work environment in order to raise the vitality of the organization and take its effective role in its survival and continued strategic superiority.
3. The research organization should more clearly increase its interest in supporting linkages, identifying the common field, and reducing environmental uncertainties that affect the conditions of the work environment so that they can carry out work tasks in a way that ensures a better stable job environment.
4. The need for the researched organization to provide effective support for the dimensions of the job fingerprint and to provide a work environment in which working individuals can communicate with each other in the organization to ensure the cross-fertilization and spread of knowledge ideas, skills and experiences, which leads to progress and prosperity in line with the dynamics of the rapidly changing environment.

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5. The need for senior management or medical staff to adopt strategic and knowledge systems that enhance the existence of trust, awareness and compatibility between the internal and external environment and the involvement of workers in strategic decisions because of its great importance in increasing the confidence of workers in their leaders and their organization and be ready to keep pace with change Stable in their work environment.
6. The need for the leaders of the researched organization to instil morale and confidence as important indicators to make the employee able to carry out work that has its imprint and excellence by presenting new cognitive ideas that contribute to achieving compatibility and keeping pace with changes in the external environment in order to achieve the concept of the functional imprint.
7. The research organization should work to the best of its ability to increase reliance on the variable of capacity support, strengthen ties and relations between co-workers, and create trust among them in a way that contributes to confronting environmental uncertainty and reducing the mobility of the environment, thus creating an atmosphere of trust between superiors and subordinates that eliminates all aspects of organizational chaos.
8. The need for senior management in the organization to eliminate the barriers of change and formulate the required future to ensure the reduction and support of strategic plans in the internal work environment and thus achieve career success.
9. The need to focus on the gaps in compatibility between organizational structures and levels that form the basis of the principles of the functional footprint.

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